

METHODICAL ANALYSIS OF LONDON SCHOOL IN MUSIC TEACHING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: This article analyzes various methods of developing students' musical skills in music lessons, reveals the advantages of the London vocal school, and comments on the relevance of using this method in the framework of the additional education system for children.

Key words: vocal, technology, art of academic singing, breathing, vocal technique.

The art of singing music occupies a special place in modern culture. Academic singing music today is not only an art form, but also a socio-cultural phenomenon. He attracts fans with his expressiveness, direct connection with movement and rhythm, emotional structure of works.

Modern singing vocal music is distinguished by its harmonic and melodic characteristics, as well as by its own arrangement rules. Therefore, the demand for academic vocal performers is increasing.

The art of music perfectly matches the interests of modern children and teenagers. In the lessons of the music group, children learn to sing correctly in any environment, including on stage, to feel free and free. Academic singing lessons help the child to act in a complex world, to feel among friends and colleagues, to develop communication skills, to expand his understanding of the world and people, to facilitate the process of social adaptation of the child, to help him in life.

Today, music is one of the main forms of solving the primary tasks of pedagogy and psychology - the development of children's creative abilities - the mass involvement of the young generation in the art of music. It is creative abilities that stimulate the formation of special qualities of the mind: the ability to observe, compare, analyze, combine, find connections and relationships - qualities that are necessary for any young person of the 21st century. Academic singing is defined as a voice between (or classical) vocals and folk vocals. Modern academic singing combines vocal and folk singing techniques, as well as a number of unique techniques specific to academic vocals. The main difference between the vocal of an academic singer and the performance of folk music is in the goals and tasks of the vocalist.

Interestingly, academic singing differs from singing not only in the style of performance, vocalization and phonation methods, but also in the use of

technical tools. The fact is that academic singers and folk singers always work within a certain canon or regulated sound, and it is not customary for them to deviate from the norm. The task of the academic singer is elsewhere - in the search for his unique voice, easily recognizable behavior, as well as a stage image. For the same reason, in the case of academic singers, there are more phrases that are difficult to sing and require rapid changes of breath, while in folk songs, the text is adapted to the music to a greater extent. Thus, the main distinctive features of the Academic singing vocal are the search and formation of the vocalist's unique performance style.

Sometimes, many people who are just beginning to understand the basics of singing technique, unconsciously, and sometimes consciously, try to imitate their favorite academic singers, blindly copy their singing style.

Practice shows that not everyone will benefit from it in the future. Everything here is individual: for some, the birth of a beautiful singing voice is a joyful surprise, for others it is the result of long and hard work. There are many social media sites where you can learn how to sing and what not to do. Currently, children's vocals, including the project "The Voice", are gaining popularity. During this project, you can see different levels of training and vocal skills. Among the participants are children and teenagers of different levels of preparation. But in most cases, the project is able to serve as a model, which is a bright result of a long process of training and mastering vocal art in harmony with natural talent, taste, developed musical ear and sense of rhythm. In our opinion, the following performances are exemplary numbers of vocal art.

This project is a unique "perfect" for modern children, serving as a unique source of inspiration, guidance, and at the same time, working with children and adolescents. it can serve as a source of inspiration and a guide for teachers. This is a unique standard culmination point, the existence of which does not allow vocal teachers to stop at the achievements, forces them to search for new knowledge, methods, technologies and improve the existing material.

Having mastered various vocal practices and methods in direct pedagogical activity, I came to a certain conclusion. Children and teenagers studying academic singing gradually form and develop vocal skills in specialized classes. This low speed also reduces the overall efficiency of the learning process. In order to change the current situation, it is logical to assume that it is necessary to increase the level of pedagogical competence in relation to vocal and methodological knowledge, and first of all, to develop the technological aspect of professional activity. It is known that the concept of "method" in translation

from the ancient Greek language means the way. To achieve success in the art of academic singing, to choose the shortest way to develop the natural abilities and talents of students - constant interest and is the key to maintaining enthusiasm.

To solve the existing professional problem, the modern vocal technique of the London vocal school was adopted. It covers almost all aspects of modern Academic singing. The technique instantly forms and develops children's singing and vocal skills, develops the child's emotional sphere, and nurtures a person capable of creativity.

The vocal methodology of the London vocal school is based on non-standard vocal exercises, which primarily helps to develop singing breath, which serves as a basis for further development of the student's vocal abilities. This method is aimed at the correct formation of the sound, the flexibility of the voice (melisma), the expansion of the range, the development of harmonic hearing and the coordination of vocal sounds, as well as the development of the sense of rhythm, which is very necessary for the vocalist, and complex vocal exercises for the development of vocal improvisation there is.

There are many well-known vocal techniques, for example: "Singing in the speech position" by Seth Riggs or the excellent vocal technique "Phonopedic method of voice development by V. V. Emelyanov". The main content of the last technique is revealed in several monographs of the author, the most famous of which is "Voice Development. Coordination and Training". The 7th edition of this book was published in 2015. Both of these methods are aimed at developing the sound technically. The main condition for performing vocal exercises at the London Vocal School is to sing with movement to the beat of the background music being played. Thus, it complicates the performance of vocal exercises and at the same time frees the student, giving him the necessary freedom in his voice, which is especially difficult for beginner vocalists to achieve when performing simple exercises without movements.

To bring out the creative potential of the student, it is not enough just to sing songs, they should be used for their purpose, that is, they should use the mastered vocal skills in mastering the song repertoire. When working with an academic singing repertoire, you cannot immediately work on dynamics, dramaturgy, voice, etc., everything must be gradual. This approach provides high-quality and fast results. First you need to learn the tone. In addition to working on intonation, it is necessary to practice breathing. It should be remembered that breathing should be taken without forgetting the phrases. At the same time, you can start working with the text. You should read it several

times and identify diction difficulties. These passages should be separated from the whole text and memorized as tongue twisters. Pronunciation speed can be accelerated. Then you need to pronounce it with expressive intonation to give semantic color to the text. In addition, the text can be spoken several more times, using emotional and vocal colors close to the melody of this song.

After that you can put everything together. The main thing is that in the end, no component is damaged. This stage is usually a little longer than all the previous ones. A song can be recorded on any available audio or video medium and evaluated objectively. Music is primarily aimed at forming and developing the child's personality, forming his creative potential and developing individual musical abilities. Engaged in the singing of future academic singers, not only mastering vocal art, unique styles of various genres of modern popular music, solo performance with piano accompaniment, but also other children also learn to work in a team.

The appearance of the room is very important. In addition, all these tools must be used in a functional way to create a holistic synthetic image. This is the complexity of the musical Academic singing number. Kuznetsov V. wrote: "One of the main features of a vocal or instrumental musical Academic singing number is the uniqueness of communicating with the audience. An academic performer will definitely attract the audience."

The interpretation of the actor is also important - this is looking at this material through his own personal situation and attitude, where the vocal technique is an active assistant of acting. Using various behavioral knowledge, the child gradually finds his own style, close to his spiritual and natural qualities.

Creating your own image is a long way, which consists of previous knowledge, practical experience, skills and mental state. "How to create your image?" - this is the main question for the singer of the vocal genre, which he must answer himself. In academic singing circles, in addition to stage skills, discipline, respect for one's own and others' time, and work are important for children. This is a very important quality in work and life. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that plasticity, acting, singing - all this should be developed not only in a child who wants to connect his life with art, but in any child.

Thus, musical and aesthetic education and vocal and technical development of schoolchildren should be interrelated and inseparable. Today, the leading place belongs to the field of additional education. Modern science has proven that children who are engaged in singing activities are more sensitive, emotional, sensitive and open. Having a voice gives the child the opportunity to sing his

feelings in a moment, and this emotional explosion fills him with vital energy. The effective use of various modern methods of developing singing skills helps the individual development of the child, the development of the cultural potential of the children's community, and forms a constructive life strategy aimed at success.

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